

Grant Report

Awarding agency: NASA

Grant Number: 80NSSC23K0854

Project Title: Ciencia Abierta Accesible: Community-Based Teaching of the TOPS OpenCore Online in Spanish

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Accomplishments

Goals and Objectives

Grant objectives NASA-approved on September 29th, 2024, grouped according to MetaDocencia's Pillars:

- **Contextualization Pillar**
 - Develop contextualized and accessible versions of the NASA TOPS OpenCore Modules for Spanish-speaking audiences.
 - As new stable versions in English of the NASA TOPS OpenCore Modules are released, update the contextualized Spanish-speaking NASA TOPS OpenCore Modules once a year.
- **Capacity Building Pillar**
 - Conditional on the public availability of an initial version of inclusive and accessible NASA TOPS OpenCore Modules, train virtual cohorts with these contents until June 30th, 2026. Each cohort will receive 6 weeks of online training covering the 5 NASA TOPS OpenCore modules in Spanish.
- **Community Building Pillar**
 - Champion NASA TOPS in low-resourced research environments through conference presentations, publications, press releases, social networks, and community activities.
 - Steward a supportive and inclusive Spanish-speaking online community around NASA TOPS training.

This grant summary is completed by MetaDocencia and their collaborators at OLS. The grant led by OLS delivers content in English, and this grant, led by MetaDocencia, is delivered primarily in Spanish.

Progress to Date

Open Science 101 was officially launched in December 2023, and a stable version of it that can be contextualized to Spanish (i.e., <https://github.com/nasa/Transform-to-Open-Science/tree/open-science-101>) is available on GitHub since February 5th, 2024. The table below shows a brief timeline of the activities and achievements undertaken to deliver this work.

July 6th, 2023	Grant Agreement Letter Received
July-September 2023	<p>Grant-wise Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ramp-up: MetaDocencia and OLS staff collaborated to design cohort training materials before the Open Science 101 official release. ● Grant update: MetaDocencia was informed that NASA TOPS will not provide a Spanish translation of slides nor the MOOC for the TOPS OpenCore Modules. This was the reification of a risk considered in the grant that required updating the original objectives. ● Anticipating the maternity leave of three team members between October 2023 and March 2024 and one team member leaving MetaDocencia in March 2024, we opened a call for new collaborators in August. We onboarded three new team members in September. <p>Capacity Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Detailed feedback (see this document) for TOPS Open Science 101 - Stage 1 Beta-test. <p>Community Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Two blog posts published during this period. ● Amplification and championing of NASA TOPS through our monthly Newsletter in Spanish (with 2,000+ readers), Spanish-speaking Slack workspace (with 700+ members), and social media (i.e., Twitter, LinkedIn, Mastodon, Instagram, and Facebook).
October-November 2023	<p>Contextualization Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On hold until the release of OpenCore materials. <p>Capacity Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Kept working toward preparations for teaching virtual cohorts.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepared and started publishing Open Access resources helpful for capacity building and agency of low-resourced research communities. <p>Community Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designed Project Polen to onboard external collaborators key for a community-based contextualization and cohort teaching. • Published blog posts and one scholarly article in Nature Human Behaviour about Open Science and AI featuring NASA TOPS. • Presented in person at Knowledge Exchange Meeting 2023, Costa Rica. • Amplification and championing of NASA TOPS through our monthly Newsletter in Spanish, Spanish-speaking Slack workspace, and social media.
<p>December 2023 -January 2024</p>	<p>Contextualization Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarization with Open Science 101 contents. <p>Capacity Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designed and launched Exploration Mision, a Spanish-speaking study group cohort to support the obtaining NASA TOPS badges using the MOOC in English for six weeks. • Published Open Access resources helpful for capacity building and agency of low-resourced research communities. <p>Community Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polen Program Launch - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10285863 • Presented at AGU2023, online. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10264924 • Amplification and championing of NASA TOPS through our monthly Newsletter in Spanish,

	<p>Spanish-speaking Slack workspace, and social media.</p>
<p>February-March 2024</p>	<p>Contextualization Pillar</p> <p>GitHub release of Open Science 101 content in February completely unblocked the work for the objectives of this pillar.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crowdin setup and continuous communication with NASA TOPS Team so contextualized contents are widely available and high-quality (e.g., including translation of images and video captioning). • Through the vote, the community decides to call the upcoming work “contextualization” in favor of other possible terms such as “translation,” “situated translation,” or “localization.” <p>Capacity Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Misión Exploración cohort continued as a Conservatory because the community asked to continue gathering once a week to talk about Open Science in Spanish. Learnings during these events inform the other two pillars. • Cohort organization for the first fully in Spanish cohort starts. <p>Community Building Pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA Symposium participation: 1 team member in person, 9 team members online, keynote presentation as a SuperUser. • Several Open-Science-related blog posts published, together with other resources helpful for community building. • Amplification and championing of NASA TOPS through our monthly Newsletter in Spanish, Spanish-speaking Slack workspace, and social media.

Opportunities for training and professional development

This project is designed to train not only the participants of the virtual cohorts, but also to build capacity with internal and external collaborators who join as experts and facilitators of all activities. Training is iterative through asynchronous resources such as open access publications (see items listed as “resource” in the Products table) and synchronous meetings.

How results were disseminated to communities of interest

Once we received the award letter in March 2023, over three months before receiving the grant agreement, we started disseminating NASA TOPS widely through all our communications means including two press pieces, social media, monthly newsletter, webpage, and Slack workspace. Since then we presented this work in one international keynote in Buenos Aires, one NASA TOPS keynote, and two international invited talks one in Costa Rica and one online (further detail in the Products table). For major milestones or announcements, we also reach out to other partner organizations that include announcements in their newsletters or Slack workspaces about results and actions of this grant (e.g., SciELO Mexico, Open Science Chan Zuckerberg Initiative), further amplifying the dissemination to communities of interest.

Plans for future

The following table presents our tentative plans from April 2024 to March 2025, the next full year of work. Throughout the initial contextualization and the first 100% Spanish Pilot Cohort, we will learn a lot about ways to improve these deliverables. We expect modifications to this timeline based on this learning until adjusting to a stable cadence of updating Spanish materials once a year and offering cohorts continuously with occasional short breaks for summer/winter.

	2024									2025		
Timeline	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D*	J*	F*	M
Contextualization	X	X										

100% in Spanish Pilot Cohort		X	X	X								
Cohort 2					X	X	X					
Cohort 3							X	X	X			
1st update to Spanish Materials										X	X	X
Championing NASA TOPS in low-resourced research environments	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X
Inclusive community building	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

* December, January, and February are slower months due to Summer Break in the Southern Cone of Latin America, where most MetaDocencia staff is located.

Products

<p>At-risk products (i.e., before receiving the grant agreement letter)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keynote presentation: NASA TOPS was featured at the Collective Creation of Open Science / Creación Colectiva de Ciencia Abierta, Keynote presentation at csv,conf,v7, Argentina, 2023. Bilingual slides - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7845473 • Press pieces: NASA TOPS was featured in Argentina’s press in Spanish here and here
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<p>July-September 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Blog post: We started to transform toward Open Science together with NASA: 10 points! Bilingual. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8233746 (EN), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8221057 (ES) ● Blog post: Uniendo comunidades para ampliar la participación en la Ciencia Abierta - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8304990 (ES)
<p>October-November 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accessibility resource for low-resourced communities: Repositorio de Accesibilidad 2022-2023 - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10514981 (ES) ● Keynote presentation video: Collective Creation of Open Science / Creación Colectiva de Ciencia Abierta, Keynote presentation at csv,conf,v7, Argentina, 2023. Recording with high-quality bilingual captions: https://youtu.be/sV_0nAypuZQ?si=Q73YLnIN-c8mD_C ● Invited scholar comment: Generative AI poses ethical challenges to Open Science, a comment for Nature Human Behaviour. Bilingual. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10210505 (EN), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10210551 (ES), blog posts including open access links to bilingual versions of: Acion, L., Rajngewerc, M., Randall, G. et al. Generative AI poses ethical challenges for open science. Nat Hum Behav 7, 1800–1801 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-023-01740-4. ● Conference Invited Talk: MetaDocencia y el enfoque comunitario hacia la ciencia y la educación abiertas - Invited presentation, Knowledge Exchange Meeting 2023, Costa Rica.

	<p>Bilingual. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10256495</p>
<p>December 2023 -January 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Infrastructure resource for low-resourced communities: Plan de Infraestructura - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10500908 ● Webpage: Misión Exploración - Conversatorio de Ciencia Abierta https://www.metadocencia.org/eventos/ ● Blog post: Polen Program Launch - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10285863 ● Conference Invited Talk: Latin American lessons learned on how to do outstanding global open source science - Invited presentation, AGU2023, online. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10264924 ● Annual Report: Reporte a la Comunidad 2023 - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10520281
<p>February-March 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Misión Exploración Blog Posts Series: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10689025 (ES), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10723812 (ES), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10785647 (ES), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10818512 (ES), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10883173 (ES). ● How to publish in academia resource for low-resourced communities: Tips for getting invited to write for an academic journal - Bilingual, https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10630693 (EN), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10627383

	<p>(ES)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual cohort organization resource for low-resourced communities: KitCo, Kit para Cohortes - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10689694 (ES) • KitCo Presentation: Estructura e infraestructura para la formación por cohortes virtuales - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10525382 (ES) • Inclusive team building resource for low-resourced communities: Cómo generar encuentro genuino y cultura del bienestar en los eventos del equipo, tanto presenciales como virtuales - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10818072 (ES) • Governance resource for low-resourced communities: Guía de incorporación Consejo Asesor (CA) - https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10669885 (ES) • Governance resource for low-resourced communities: Advisory Committee (AC) Offboarding Guide - Bilingual. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10671869 (EN), https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10669885 (ES)
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Participants & Other Collaborating Organizations

Change in Personnel: The major grant change in September required the following changes in personnel at no additional cost to NASA:

- The number of Co-Is was reduced by one to allow for more flexibility in hiring Other Personnel. Thus, Irene Vazano graciously accepted to resign as Co-I.

- For personal reasons that kept her from a longer commitment and due to other obligations, Melissa Black stepped down as a Co-I. Nicolas Palopoli stepped up in her place instead.
- Laura Ascenzi, Paz Míguez, Julián Buede, Paola Lefer, and Iván Poggio were added as Other Personnel.

Other Collaborating Organizations: A key goal for MetaDocencia was to gather early feedback from Spanish speakers both based within and outside the US to build a diverse community that can work together at contextualizing the NASA TOPS Open Science 101 contents. Misión Exploración was very successful at knitting new ties with organizations such as SciELO México (i.e., [SciELO](#) has been a major contributor to Open Science in Latin America since 1997), the [Charles Darwin Foundation Galapagos](#), or [OpenlabEc](#) in Ecuador, among others.

The visibility the NASA TOPS Team facilitated to MetaDocencia at the NASA TOPS Symposium was essential to strengthen our ties with other NASA TOPS grantees, such as:

- National Louis University, a Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI), with whom we have submitted the proposal 23-SOSS23-0031 “Research Practice Partnership to Support Open Science Implementation” to standardize the way to measure NASA TOPS Open Science 101 impact and who is introducing us to the national HSI hub,
- NASA ARSET, catering content to a large audience of Spanish-speaking remote sensing researchers, and
- Columbia University and 106C Million Concepts are interested in contextualizing their ScienceCore materials to Spanish to reach Spanish speakers.

Impact

We are still developing a standardized way to measure the impact of this grant. From the data we have gathered so far, we know that:

- 94 participants from 18 countries signed up for Misión Exploración, 83 (88% attended at least one of the 9 synchronous events) with a mean assistance of 24 participants (min = 16, max = 33) and a mean of 83% of attendees stayed until the end of the session.
- As a measure of participant satisfaction, we report the Net Promoter Score (NPS). After each session, we asked participants to rate on a scale of 1 to 10 how likely they would be to (1) recommend the activity to someone else. We collected a total of 72 responses. we obtained an NPS of 79.2%. An NPS above 20% is considered favorable, and above 50% is excellent.
- Our incomplete records show that at least 21 participants (25.3% of those who attended at least one session) obtained their NASA TOPS golden badge.
- 74% of the audience manifested interest in the activity to expand their knowledge about open science, to acquire tools for their practice, and to practice open science
- After each meeting, we asked participants to share one thing they liked about the encounter and would like to keep. We grouped responses qualitatively into the following categories (ordered from most to least often mentioned):
 - **Multiple perspectives and discussion:** comments regarding interdisciplinarity, the space to share experiences and perspectives, and how enriching different points of view can be.
 - **Format and presentation:** comments regarding the participative format, how the sessions were led, and the materials shared, such as slides and shared documents.
 - **Latin American context** and **Spanish language:** comments that explicitly mentioned these subjects.
 - **Content:** includes comments referring specifically to the information shared during the meeting.

- **Community:** comments that explicitly mention the word “community” but also those highlighting the importance of a shared experience.
- After each meeting, we asked participants to share suggestions to improve the encounters. We grouped responses into the following categories (ordered from most to least often mentioned):
 - **Longer meetings:** suggestions to extend the duration of the meetings.
 - **Organize interactions:** comments regarding how the attendees participated and how this can be distracting in some cases.
 - **Extend the discussion:** refers to the suggestion of making other channels of communication available to discuss these subjects asynchronously, through the use of the shared document, and also to the suggestion of participating in breakout rooms.
 - **Translate the content in English:** comments regarding the content’s language as a barrier.
 - **Relate reading materials to Latin America, Limit hipertextuality** (referring to the number of links and external references in the material), **Present a map of the subject, Create a repository that centralizes first steps, Overlap of materials, Timing,** and **Expand on the applicability across fields** were also mentioned explicitly.

A full report with more insights and the code used to analyze the data collected can be found at:

https://github.com/MetaDocencia/reportes-publicos/tree/main/mision_exploracion

Changes/Problems

Changes in approach and reasons for change

Since the September modification, the project has run smoothly.

Changes that had a significant impact on expenditures

Receiving the grant agreement on July 6th (rather than before June 1st when the grant period started) and the changes required have resulted in lower expenditure than anticipated.